

Arsenic Polluted Ground Water in Eastern U P, India

Akbare Azam

Assistant Professor Department of Chemistry, Government Women P G College Ghazipur U.P, INDIA

ABSTRACT

River Basin reported worldwide in recent studies which causes many adverse effects not only for drinking but also for irrigation purpose. Accumulation of arsenic in soil through contaminated ground water during irrigation, which is uptake by many edible parts of plants and subsequently transferred in other food chain. This paper shows the Uttar Pradesh and Bihar situated in the middle and upper Gangetic belt.

Keywords--- DSM, MSMA, Environment

I. INTRODUCTION

Access to pure water either for drinking or agricultural purpose is a first goal and a key target for every nation. But due to some natural and anthropogenic reason it's still challenge for many countries. The pollution of soil and water with Arsenic (As) is one of the most important environmental problems globally. Natural as well as anthropogenic activities are the main reason for a coverlet of arsenic contamination in ground water and soil. These contaminated ground water and soil are the major source of arsenic in food chain and other food trophic level. Presence of Arsenic considered as one of the hazardous elements in the environment and exposure of it causes serious health issues arise like cardiovascular, neurological, hematological, renal, and respiratory problems. Groundwater Arsenic contamination in Eastern Gangetic River Basin reported worldwide in recent studies which causes many adverse effects not only for drinking but also for irrigation purpose. Accumulation of arsenic in soil through contaminated ground water during irrigation, which is uptake by many edible parts of plants and subsequently transferred in other food chain. Uttar Pradesh and Bihar situated in the middle and upper Gangetic belt. According to Chakraborty et al. [2] surveyed report on the in the Ganga-Meghna-Brahmaputra (GMB) region, a large population nearly 500 million people are facing arsenic problem having in area approx. 500,000 km². The conversion of arsenic oxidation state and their presence in ground water or soil depends upon various environmental conditions. It can be recognized in three forms: Inorganic, organic, and arsine gas. Arsenic presents as in trivalent (+3) oxidation state (like arsenic trioxide, sodium arsenite, and arsenic trichloride) and in pentavalent (+5)

state (like arsenates, arsenic pentoxide and arsenic acid). Interconversion of Arsenate form (+5) into arsenite form (+3) conditionally in oxidized and reduced condition, which is the most toxic form of arsenic. The conversion of more toxic inorganic form to less toxic organoarsenic compound such as disodium methylarsenate (DSMA) and monosodium methylarsenate (MSMA) formation via organism known as Biomethylation [3]. Hypothesis: Distribution of Arsenic in Ganga River Basin: The River Ganges is very complicated hydrology and geological point of view in the Ganges Delta region. The Ganga river basin and its tributaries spread on a very large coverage area in India and Bangladesh. It spread and bed covering four countries (China, Nepal, India and Bangladesh) and eleven states of India (West Bengal, Himanchal Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Madhya Pradesh, Chattisgarh, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Jharkhand, Punjab, Haryana, Rajasthan and Territory of Delhi). Combinedly the Ganges Meghna Brahmaputra (GMB) basin is a bed covering across Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal, and China. From the origin Gangotri glacier Ganga river water discharge Passover into three segments. It extended as upper, middle and lower Gangetic belt.

Uttar Pradesh comes under upper and Middle Ganga plain. Himalayan Mountain and Tibet plateau, considered as the biggest source of arsenic contamination in the Gangetic region and this contamination are evidently becoming life threatening in almost every year [4]. Geographically Uttar Pradesh situated in the northern region of India and border of Nepal. The river Ganga and Ghaghara are two major river flows from northeast to southeast. First time in UP arsenic introduced as a contaminant in Ballia district. Status of Arsenic Contamination in Eastern U.P.: In U.P. Jal Nigam and UNICEF combinedly reported and identified in 18 districts. Arsenic above the 50 ppb limit for drinking and Arsenic according to WHO limit was found in 31 districts. Times of India also reported "Ground water arsenic contamination of Uttar Pradesh exceeds to the value of BIS (Bureau of Indian Standards) permissible limit of 0.01 mg/liter across 31 districts of the state. Arsenic contamination in Ballia district: District Ballia is located in the eastern part of UP with shared in 17 blocks.

The Ganga is main river basin and also drained with river Ghagra on the north and Chhoti Sargu in the south. Agriculture is the main activity (72%) because of having high poverty (nearly 44%) and 58% low literacy rate. For irrigation purpose people depend on ground water, tube well and number of tal and canals like surhatal, sikandar purlal. In Ballia contamination of arsenic compared to west Bengal where arsenic exceeding 50 µg/l. District Laboratory of U.P. Jal Nigam also Confirmed Arsenic confirmatory tests by spectrophotometer. High arsenic concentration has been found in all 16 blocks out of 17 blocks of ground water on Belthara Road, Nagra, Rasra, Chilkahar, Pandah, Navanagar, Beruarwari, Gharwar, Hanumanganj, Maniyar, Sohaon, Dubhad, Bansdeh Revati, Beriya, Belhari and Murlichapra blocks from 14 to 820 ppb which is much higher than prescribed drinking value by WHO. The Arsenic Task Force (ATF) has been reported that the presence of poisonous arsenic affected approximately 1.20 lakh people in 55 villages of three blocks (Revti, Dubahar, Belhra) in Ballia.

II. ROLE OF SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS IN ARSENIC POISONING

This finding of a statistically significant relationship between arsenicosis and household income may be explained by a number of possible causal factors. According to the National Research Council: "Variability in arsenic metabolism appears to be important in understanding the human response. There is evidence that methylating capacity differs among individuals and population groups. Different capacities would result in variations in tissue concentrations of arsenic. Also, environmental factors, particularly diet, might be important in explaining susceptibility." (National Research Council, p193, 1999). In humans, the liver methylates inorganic arsenic that is consumed in drinking water. The resulting arsenic metabolites are excreted in the urine. Differences in methylating efficiency may be the reason for variations in arsenic retained in the body, and thus susceptibility to arsenic poisoning.

In this context, it will also be important to establish gender differences in exposure and effect. Social roles are likely to affect amount and duration of exposure, and the issue of gender differences in susceptibility to environmental contaminants and carcinogens is increasingly being addressed (IOM 1998). Hsueh et al. (1995) found that chronic carriers of hepatitis B with liver dysfunction had a significantly increased prevalence of skin cancer. This evidence indicates that those with liver disorders have a diminished ability to methylate inorganic arsenic, as suggested by Buchet et al. (1984). Therefore, one hypothesis would be that there is a negative relationship between the prevalence of liver disorders and household income. However, this could not be verified using the data from the Samta demographic survey. Evidence suggests that the role of nutrition may also be important in determining methylation efficiency and toxicity to arsenic retained in the body. Yang and Blackwell (1961)

studied nutritional factors in the blackfoot endemic region of China (Province of Taiwan).

Their results indicated that residents of this region consume a diet low in protein, and in particular the amino acid methionine. Vahter and Marafante (1987) found that a low amount of methionine or protein in the diet decreased methylation of inorganic arsenic in the rabbit. In addition, insufficient vitamin intake, in particular vitamin B₁₂, might reduce the ability of the body to methylate arsenic (Buchet and Lauwerys 1985). For these reasons, women, whose nutritional levels are frequently deficient in South Asian countries for reasons linked with cultural norms and reproductive function, may be at particular risk. It is also suggested that zinc and selenium may provide protection against the toxic effects of accumulated levels of arsenic in the body (National Research Council 1999). It is suggested that the diet of blackfoot disease patients in China (Province of Taiwan) is deficient in zinc and selenium (Pan et al. 1996).

The National Research Council (1999) notes that there is still uncertainty over the relative importance of the various nutritional factors, and calls for more research into the issue. The Asia Arsenic Network (AAN) researchers indicated however, that household income might serve as a good proxy for nutritional intake in Samta Village (Tani, 1999a;b). Consequently, they ascribed an important part of the negative relationship between prevalence and household income to this explanation. For an accurate estimation of nutritional intake, it is also important to take into account patterns of intra-household food distribution, which may favour or disadvantage various family members by age or sex, and which cannot be seen through the general category of household income. However, household income might also be related to water practices in the village. The importance of water storage techniques has been highlighted by Alaerts (1999). He highlights the example of the water storage practices of people in the Laxipur area of Bangladesh. In this area water is stored in small vessels to allow the iron oxide to settle on the bottom of the vessel and this enhances the concentration of adsorbed arsenic in the sludge. Higher income households might have greater storage facilities for their tubewell water and might consequently be able to store the water for longer.

If higher income households are using water that has been allowed to settle for a period before drinking, then this could help to explain the observed arsenicosis-income relationship. Unfortunately, we are currently not informed about longer-term water storage practices in Samta Village. In Bangladesh it is likely that access to tubewell drinking water will be at least partially determined by social status. Therefore, the observed relationship between arsenicosis prevalence and household income could be due to social barriers to access to arsenic-free water for poor households.

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